

24 PULSE AC-DC CONVERTERS FOR IMPROVED POWER QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

Issues of power quality are mainly concerned with the deviation of the current or voltage from its ideal waveform. The major cause of this deviation is because of the harmonics introduced by the switching of solid state devices. Such devices are of vital importance in the multiple pulse power electronic converter devices. All the switches used for power conversion will inject harmonics and all together leads to a power quality issue or event accordingly. In the present work power quality of such converters are improved by increasing the number pulses required for their operation. The present paper brings out 24 pulse controlled converter and the results obtained are compared with the performance of 18 pulse controlled converter. Fast Fourier Transform analysis is carried out on all the said converters and found that with the increase in number of pulses, total harmonic distortion is having a considerable reduction leading to improved power quality.

KEYWORDS: Converters, Harmonics, Multiple Pulse, Power Quality

1. INTRODUCTION

Large amount of harmonics, poor power factor and high total harmonic distortion (THD) in the utility interface are common problems when non-linear loads such as adjustable speed drives, power supplies, induction heating systems, UPS systems and SMPS are connected to the electric utility. In several cases, the interface to the electric utility is processed with three-phase uncontrolled diode bridge rectifier. Due to the nonlinear nature of load, the input line currents have significant harmonics. The power quality of power supply of an ideal power system means to supply electric energy with perfect sinusoidal wave form at a constant frequency of a specified voltage with least amount of disturbances. However the harmonic is one of the major factor due to which none of condition is fulfilled in practice. The presence of harmonics disturbs the waveform shape of voltage and current and increases the current level and changes the power factor of supply and which in turn creates many problems.

The electricity is produced and distributed in its fundamental form as 50 Hz in India. A harmonics is defined as the content of signal whose frequency is integral multiple of the system fundamental frequency. Due to harmonic effect the sinusoidal wave form is no longer have stand and it become non-sinusoidal or complex wave form. The complex waveform consists of a fundamental wave of 50 Hz and a number of other sinusoidal waves whose frequencies are integral multiple of fundamental wave like 2f(100hz), 3f (150 Hz), 4f (200 Hz) etc. Wave having frequency of 2f, 4f, 6f etc are called the even harmonics and those having frequency of 3f, 5f, 7f etc are called as odd harmonics. When fundamental frequency is super imposed with high-level harmonics it results into complex wave and which is non sinusoidal. Many methodologies have appeared in the field of multi-pulse converters, many giving new concepts and verifying their claims by simulations and experimental work. Paice [1, 7] proposed maximizing the efficiency of a 12 pulse AC-DC